

Synthesis of Pyrimidine Schiff Bases as Anticancer Agents.

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Some pyrimidine Schiff's bases were synthesised by condensing 6-amino uracil with different substituted benzaldehydes and few heterocyclic aldehydes. The compounds were also tested for anticancer activity and were found inactive against WM-256 tumour system.

THE literature survey reveals that thousands of organic compounds are synthesised and tested for anticancer activity. A series of inert azo compounds containing nitrogen mustard moiety were synthesised¹ and found active against Walker rat carcinoma 256. As isosteres of the azo mustards a large number of Schiff bases were prepared²⁻⁴ and tested against Dunning leukemia in rats. Modi, Sabnis and Deliwala⁵ have prepared some Schiff bases mustard and screened for antitumour activity. Many of the compounds displayed significant activity against L 1210 Lymphoid leukemia, Walker 256 (intramuscular) and Dunning leukemia. Schiff bases⁶ without having alkylating nitrogen mustard moiety were synthesised and 4-n-hexyl-6-(2-Hydroxy-phenylimino methyl)-resorcinol was found most active against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma, Sarcoma-180 and Yoshida sarcoma. It has been suggested that azo-methine linkage might be responsible for the activity. Schiff bases are hydrolysed readily under mild acidic conditions. Since majority of tumour cells are at lower pH than cells in normal tissue⁷, the compounds could be selectively hydrolysed by the tumour cells. Hydrolysis of these compounds *in vivo* may liberate the active aldehyde to act as alkylating agent and at the same time the pyrimidine is freed to act as antimetabolite. The azomethine linkage may be operative by a postulated chelation mechanism.

Chakraborti and Kumar De⁸ have reported Schiff bases of 5-amino uracil with substituted benzaldehydes. In order to see whether the change in the position of amino group in uracil and nature of the aldehyde have any effect on anticancer activity, the present paper describes the synthesis of twelve pyrimidine Schiff bases of 4 or 6-amino uracil with substituted benzaldehydes and heterocyclic aldehydes such as pyridine 2-aldehyde, pyridine-4-aldehyde, thienyl-2-aldehyde and furfuraldehyde.

The constitution of these compounds were confirmed by their elemental analysis and UV and IR spectra. The absorption of pyrimidine peak around 260 nm has been shifted to higher wavelength i.e. 290-300 nm in these compounds. This may be because of extended conjugation existing with the aromatic nucleus. In

all these compounds absence of N-H stretching band (3400 cm^{-1} to 3500 cm^{-1}) and the presence of C=N stretching band (1680 cm^{-1} to 1726 cm^{-1}) shows the formation of Schiff bases.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in thiels tube containing liquid paraffin and are uncorrected. The ultraviolet spectra were measured in ethanol solution, with Hitachi Model 124 Recording spectrophotometer. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Perkin-Elmer 337. The samples were dried in vacuo over calcium chloride for micro analysis. 4 or 6-amino uracil used were of Fluka grade. The aromatic aldehydes were freshly distilled or crystallised before using. The heterocyclic aldehydes used were also of Fluka grade.

The experimental procedure for the preparation of 6-(2'-chlorobenzylideneamino) uracil is described here as a representative case.

Synthesis of 6-(2'-chloro benzylideneamino) uracil : 6-amino uracil (0.76 g., 6m moles) was dissolved in 60 ml of hot distilled water. To this solution was added (0.85 g, 6m moles) of freshly distilled *o*-chloro benzaldehyde in 20 ml of ethanol and the mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hr. 120° - 25° on sand bath and left at room temperature overnight. The crystalline solid deposited was filtered, washed with hot water and alcohol. The product was crystallised from ethanol to give pure 6-(2'-chloro benzylideneamino) uracil. M. P. 285° (D). Yield 1.5 g (70%).

By following the above procedure all other Schiff bases were prepared using aromatic aldehydes and heterocyclic aldehydes. The compounds synthesised are described in the Table.

Activity : The compounds were sent for testing the anticancer activity to C. D. R. I., Lucknow, (U. P.). They were screened against Walker tumour-256 at a dosage of 100 mg/kg and found to be ineffective. All the drugs showed a treated/control percentage between 72-141.

